

Potential impacts and priority areas of research of the on-going invasion of green crabs along the SW Atlantic

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Manuscripts

1 **Potential impacts and priority areas of research of the on-going invasion of green**
2 **crabs along the SW Atlantic**

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20

21 **Abstract**

22 The European green crab (*Carcinus maenas*) is one of the most extensively
23 studied decapod species worldwide and it currently inhabits every continent except
24 Antarctica. Its effects are observed across various spatio-temporal scales, impacting a
25 wide range of taxa and environments. While extensive research has been conducted in

26 the Northern Hemisphere, populations in the Southern Hemisphere (e.g., Argentina,
27 Australia, and South Africa) have not been thoroughly investigated. This study has three
28 main goals: 1) summarise and contextualise the invasion history of green crabs in the
29 Southwest Atlantic since their initial detection in 2000, 2) present nine case studies
30 identifying the potential ecological and economic impacts of green crabs on coastal
31 ecosystems and to highlight priority research areas, and 3) discuss appropriate
32 management actions in response to the species' rapid spread in the region. Our findings
33 suggest that green crabs are likely to impact foundation species along rocky shores, alter
34 the physical characteristics of soft-bottom environments, and affect infaunal organisms
35 in sandy shores. Most of these impacts are either occurring or expected to occur in
36 numerous marine protected areas. We also examine green crab interactions with other
37 key species, highlighting its dual role as both an invasive predator and prey for native
38 species, thus serving as a novel food resource. Furthermore, we consider their effects on
39 commercially important species, tourism, and implications for threatened native species.
40 Finally, we recommend prioritising prevention and rapid response strategies for
41 managing green crab invasions, emphasising the importance of early detection and
42 prompt action to address new incursions.

43

44 **Keywords**

45 *Carcinus maenas*. Biological invasions. Atlantic Patagonia. Ecological effects. Trophic
46 interactions. Management strategies.

47

48 **Introduction**

49 The introduction of non-native species constitutes a substantial threat to global
50 biodiversity (IPBES 2023), exerting multiple pervasive effects on ecosystems. These

51 introductions can potentially disrupt species interactions and global ecological processes
52 (Kamenova et al. 2017), while also causing major economic losses (Diagne et al. 2021).
53 In the broadest sense, non-native species have important impacts on different aspects of
54 human dimensions including culture, religion, human health, safety, and livelihoods
55 (Bortolus & Schwindt 2022).

56 The continuous introduction of non-native species is a worldwide environmental
57 problem, as invasion rates have dramatically increased alongside technological
58 advances and maritime trade (Essl et al. 2015; Hulme 2021). Despite this, the effects of
59 marine non-native species are poorly documented and significant gaps exist in our
60 knowledge regarding how these invasions can impact native biodiversity (Katsanevakis
61 et al. 2014; Schwindt et al. 2022). Understanding these changes is of paramount
62 importance to generate and support management strategies, especially those related to
63 prevention, early detection, and rapid response. Once marine non-native species are
64 established the effective ability to control, eradicate, and contain is limited and becomes
65 ineffective, as they are time-consuming, and a high-cost endeavour (Mabin et al. 2020;
66 Grosholz et al. 2021).

67 The European green crab, *Carcinus maenas*, stands out as one of the most
68 extensively studied decapod species worldwide, and numerous reviews regarding both
69 native and invasive populations are already available elsewhere (Klassen & Locke
70 2007; Leignel et al. 2014; Young & Elliot 2020; Ens et al. 2022; Frederich & Lancaster
71 2024). Successfully colonising all continents except Antarctica, this invasive species
72 has earned a place on the IUCN list as one of the world's 100 worst invaders (Lowe et
73 al. 2000). Green crabs possess biological traits that contribute to their invasion success
74 such as physiological tolerance to fluctuating environmental conditions (Tepolt &
75 Somero 2014; Young & Elliot 2020), extensive phenotypic and behavioural plasticity

76 (Todd et al. 2012; Souza et al. 2019), and high fecundity and reproductive success
77 (Monteiro et al. 2022) with long-lived feeding larval stages (Crothers 1968) that
78 facilitate distant transport and rapid dispersion. This species is known for its substantial
79 voracity, notable aggressiveness, and generalist diet (Baeta et al. 2006; Cordone et al.
80 2022), along with phenotype-environment associations that enhance its camouflage
81 abilities. These traits enable it to colonise a diverse range of environments, from
82 sheltered rocky shores to soft bottoms (Stevens et al. 2014; Cosham et al. 2016).

83 The arrival of green crabs in the Southwest Atlantic (SWA hereafter) has the
84 potential to elicit major changes in the dynamics of the region. This could be due to
85 their broad plasticity in occupying different habitat types, such as rocky shores, salt
86 marshes, sandy and muddy bottoms along with their ability to thrive in both intertidal
87 and subtidal habitats. Since its first detection on the SWA coast in 2000 (Vinuesa 2007),
88 little research has been conducted in the region despite its rapid spread. As a result, the
89 ecological consequences of the on-going invasion remain almost undocumented.
90 Furthermore, research in the SWA has focused almost exclusively on describing certain
91 aspects of the invasion in rocky intertidal areas, overlooking how the species performs
92 in other environments (e.g. soft bottoms).

93 Global evidence shows that the effects of green crabs occur at multiple spatio-
94 temporal scales and affect a broad spectrum of taxa and environments (Davis et al.
95 1998; Jamieson et al. 1998; Anton et al. 2019; Ens et al. 2022). Potential impacts could
96 be of significant importance within marine protected areas and for species of notable
97 ecological or commercial value (Grosholz et al. 2011; Iacarella et al. 2019). Considering
98 that the distribution of the species may extend, or have already extended, to areas
99 considered of high conservation value, further studies are necessary to strategically
100 define coastal sectors for implementing preventive measures. Our specific aims are

101 threefold: 1) to summarise and contextualise the state of knowledge of green crabs in
102 the SWA, 2) to present several case studies in which we identify potential ecological
103 and economic impacts of green crabs at different levels in coastal ecosystems,
104 recognising priority areas of research, and 3) to discuss appropriate management
105 decisions in light of the rapid spread of the species in the region.

106

107 **1. State of knowledge along the SWA**

108 The first detection of green crabs in Atlantic Patagonia was documented in 2000
109 by Vinuesa (2007) in Comodoro Rivadavia and Rada Tilly (45°51' S, southern Chubut
110 province in the San Jorge Gulf, Fig. 1). The introduction is hypothesised to have
111 occurred at the Comodoro Rivadavia harbour, most likely through the ballast waters of
112 an oil vessel (Hidalgo et al. 2005), although biofouling could not be ruled out. At
113 present, green crabs are distributed along a seven-degree latitudinal gradient, from San
114 Blas Bay (40°31' S) in the north to Puerto Deseado (47°45' S) in the south, including all
115 gulfs in Atlantic Patagonia (San Jorge, Nuevo, San José, and San Matías gulfs) (Barón
116 et al. 2007; Torres & González-Pisani 2016; Malvé et al. 2020; Müller Baigorria et al.
117 2022). In the SWA, green crabs inhabit two biogeographic provinces, the Magellanic
118 and Argentinean provinces and its spread is expected to continue northward and
119 southward, as predicted by species distribution models (Compton et al. 2010; Malvé et
120 al. 2020; Vera-Escalona et al. 2023). This invasive species is likely to colonise
121 embayments, lagoons, mangroves, and/or estuaries along northern Argentina, Uruguay,
122 and southern Brazil, similar to observations in other regions (Hampton & Griffiths
123 2007; Behrens Yamada & Gillespie 2008).

124 Compared to other regions worldwide, little research has been conducted on the
125 biology and ecology of green crabs in the SWA, as evidenced by the relatively low

126 number of published articles (less than 20) since their first detection in 2000. The
127 following outlines the main findings from studies conducted so far. The reproductive
128 season in San Jorge Gulf starts in early summer (January); male moult occurs mainly in
129 spring (November) and female moult in summer (between January and early March),
130 while larvae appear in spring (Vinuesa 2007). It has been shown that carapace
131 morphology alone can be used to identify sex, and that carapaces belonging to either sex
132 can be reliably identified by visual inspection of their contour (Ledesma et al. 2010). In
133 Camarones Bay, green crabs feed on slow-moving and sessile animals, including the
134 abundant mussel *Perumytilus purpuratus*, with much greater voracity than native
135 predators (Hidalgo et al. 2007). In Nuevo Gulf, diet studies based on metabarcoding,
136 direct stomach observation, and stable isotope analysis revealed a highly diverse
137 number of prey (Cordone et al. 2022). Green crab predation was also reported on the
138 edible snail *Buccinastrum deforme*, one of the most important gastropod fisheries
139 resources in northern Patagonia (Márquez et al. 2024). In this regard, green crabs are
140 positioned as a key predator in the intertidal food web, consuming prey from different
141 trophic levels. It also exhibits the capacity to exert top-down control, thereby decreasing
142 food web stability through its impacts (Cordone et al. 2023). Green crabs represent a
143 novel food resource for the opportunistic native kelp gull (*Larus dominicanus*) that
144 consumes them throughout the year (Yorio et al. 2020; Lisnizer et al. 2024). Invasive
145 green crabs are infected by more microparasites than native crabs (Frizzera et al. 2021),
146 and a new parasite (*Agmasoma* sp.) was described for a green crab population of the
147 SWA (Bojko et al. 2023). Green crab populations invading Argentina might face
148 varying degrees of success depending on the pollution levels in the environment, as
149 evidenced by differences in the development rate of their blood cells in polluted and
150 non-polluted sites (Frizzera et al. 2022). Finally, a recent study found that exposure to

151 diesel oil caused increased mortality and severe developmental abnormalities in *C.*
152 *maenas*, including malformations in chelipeds, pereopods, gill chambers, and eye
153 peduncles, which disrupted feeding and locomotion, potentially affecting population
154 dynamics and commercial viability (González Pisani et al. 2024).

155 Since its first detection green crabs have been highly successful in colonising
156 vast areas along the coastline (Figure 1). However, the hypothesis that only one
157 introduction event has occurred and then spread from the initial point of entry requires
158 thorough genetic evaluation. Currently, abundance data is largely lacking, fragmentary,
159 and/or out-dated. So far, only three abundance surveys are available for the SWA, but
160 used different methodologies hampering comparisons. Barón et al. (2007) sampled
161 several sites in San Jorge Gulf and adjacent areas when the invasion was incipient,
162 finding maximum abundances at Mazaredo (47°04' S, located in southern San Jorge
163 Gulf, Santa Cruz province, Fig. 1). Recently, Müller Baigorria et al. (2022) observed
164 higher crab densities in salt marshes compared to rocky shores at a single locality
165 (40°48' S, Las Grutas, Río Negro province, Fig. 1). In a subsequent study, Müller
166 Baigorria (2024) reported that green crabs were present year-round, with higher
167 densities in the upper mesolittoral during the warmer months. This scarcity of data
168 highlights the importance of periodically assessing abundance and distribution patterns
169 in the region to evaluate management actions.

170 Green crab populations in Atlantic Patagonia represent the southernmost
171 occurrence of the species worldwide. Notably, the southern boundary at Puerto
172 Deseado, Santa Cruz province (47°S), has remained stable since 2006, suggesting a
173 potential dispersal limitation or impaired larval development at lower temperatures (de
174 Rivera et al. 2007). It is also unknown whether strong wave action along the southern
175 shoreline may be limiting their dispersion, as observed in South Africa (Hampton &

176 Griffiths 2007), or if green crabs have reached the edges of their thermal range. Lack of
177 sampling in the area and/or low shipping connectivity with southern ports cannot be
178 discarded as potential explanations. This scenario demands closer examination,
179 particularly in light of the detection of green crabs in Alaska (Davis 2022), as was
180 predicted by early models (Hines et al. 2004).

181 As previously mentioned, the possibility of multiple introductions events cannot
182 be ruled out. In fact, we hypothesise a scenario of multiple introductions with high
183 propagule pressure, but confirmation via genetic analysis is needed. The only genetic
184 study involving green crabs from Argentina (Camarones Bay) was performed by
185 Darling et al. (2008) and revealed that the Argentinean individuals (n=15) were most
186 closely related to the Australian and Tasmanian populations suggesting a secondary
187 introduction. These authors examined genetic patterns across multiple introductions of
188 green crabs worldwide and only identified *C. maenas* using both mitochondrial and
189 nuclear markers. However, the presence of *C. aestuarii* has been recently detected in
190 Nuevo Gulf by means of mitochondrial DNA (Frizzera et al. 2021; Cordone et al.
191 2022). Confirmation about the presence of *C. aestuarii* in the SWA by the use of more
192 sensitive markers such as microsatellite *loci* (Tepolt et al. 2006) should be the next step.
193 Given that multiple introduction events involving both species could increase the
194 likelihood of hybridisation, it is crucial to conduct further genetic analyses to determine
195 whether hybridising populations exist in Argentina, as observed in South Africa (Mabin
196 et al. 2022). Interspecific hybridization is a crucial process driving adaptive
197 evolutionary change and recent research has highlighted its potential to profoundly
198 affect the establishment, propagation, and impact of invasive populations (Darling
199 2011).

200

201 **2. Potential impacts of green crabs and priority areas of research**

202 In this section, we present a diverse range of scenarios regarding current and
203 potential impacts of green crabs, as well as interactions with various native and non-
204 native species interactions that have already been established in the region (Fig. 2).

205 While these case studies focus on the SWA coast, they are discussed and contextualised
206 broadly, considering the impacts documented in other regions worldwide. This
207 approach aims to identify priority areas for further research and management.

208

209 **2.1. Effects of green crabs upon foundation species on rocky shores**

210 Mid-intertidal rocky shore communities of the SWA are uniform in appearance,
211 dominated by two species of small-size scorched mussels that form dense monocultures
212 (*Brachidontes rodriguezii* towards the north, and *Perumytilus purpuratus* towards the
213 south) (Adami et al. 2018). Other bivalve species of much greater size but more
214 abundant in the low intertidal and shallow subtidal (*Mytilus* spp. and *Aulacomya atra*),
215 are also present. In Atlantic Patagonia, because of the harsh physical environment,
216 mussel beds act as foundation species facilitating most invertebrates that live on rocky
217 shores and within its matrix (Silliman et al. 2011).

218 The impacts of green crabs on these communities are not well studied, but it was
219 shown that *P. purpuratus* is an important item in their diet (Hidalgo et al. 2005;
220 Cordone et al. 2022) suggesting that foundation species and its associated fauna along
221 the SWA coast could be significantly affected by the invasion of this species. In
222 addition, green crabs are preyed upon by native predators (see section 2.8), which in
223 some cases also include mussels in their diet (Yorio & Bertellotti 2002; Marinao et al.
224 2018). Therefore, further studies are needed to understand direct and indirect predator-
225 prey interactions on rocky shores along the recently invaded coastal area.

226 In the rocky intertidal food web of Nuevo Gulf, green crabs occupy a high trophic
227 level and represent one of the species with the largest number of prey (Cordone et al.
228 2022). In this community, a reconstruction of the local food web showed that green
229 crabs are potential competitors with at least ten other predators, sharing more than 75%
230 of their prey (Cordone et al. 2023). Among these potential competitors are mobile
231 species that can consume prey outside the intertidal zone, including birds such as
232 *Calidris alba* and *Charadrius falklandicus*, as well as fishes like *Helcogrammoides*
233 *cunninghami*, *Ribeiroclinus eigenmanni*, *Patagonotothen cornucola*, and
234 *Patagonotothen sima*. Additionally, there are sessile or sedentary invertebrates such as
235 sea anemones *Anthothoe chilensis*, *Diadumene lineata*, the isopod *Serolis* sp., and the
236 snail *Trophon geversianus* with smaller foraging areas feeding exclusively within the
237 rocky intertidal zone (Cordone et al. 2023). This food web reconstruction also showed
238 that the incorporation of green crabs into the rocky intertidal zone of Nuevo Gulf altered
239 key network properties. Two network properties were affected: modularity and quasi-
240 sing stability (Cordone et al. 2023). Modularity reflects how strongly species subgroups
241 interact with species in other subgroups and is related to the network's ability to transfer
242 information (Krause et al. 2003; Newman & Girvan 2004). In this case, the
243 incorporation of green crabs increased food web modularity, resulting in a more
244 interconnected food web with a higher probability of disturbance propagation. In turn,
245 quasi-sing stability measures the probability that a network will return to its equilibrium
246 point after a small perturbation; in other words, it assesses the web's ability to withstand
247 minor disturbances (Allesina & Pascual 2008). In this context, the presence of green
248 crabs decreased the food web's capacity to withstand small and long-range disturbances,
249 increasing the risk of negative effects on other species within the community (Cordone
250 et al. 2023).

251 The potential impact of green crab predation on foundation species like scorched
252 mussels, and the resulting adverse top-down effects on associated organisms, is
253 increasingly being recognized (Cordone et al. 2023). Green crabs generally select
254 smaller sized prey items (<25 mm) over larger ones (Walton et al. 2002; Floyd &
255 Williams 2004), which could hinder ecological successions if they prey on recruits. This
256 is particularly critical in the region given that the vast majority of the intertidal native
257 species depend upon the refuge and ameliorating conditions that foundation species
258 provide (Silliman et al. 2011). For instance, if the spread and/or cover of mussel beds
259 are reduced due to intense predation pressure, it could result in a drastic decline in rocky
260 shore biodiversity.

261 Recently, a scorched mussel mass mortality event was reported in Nuevo Gulf,
262 and it took less than a year for mussel cover to drop from 90% to almost 0% (Mendez et
263 al. 2021). While the causes of this mass mortality are not yet well understood,
264 heatwaves are thought to be one of the potential explanations. As a result, local
265 biodiversity on rocky shores has drastically declined within this gulf (Mendez et al.
266 2021). Given the disappearance of extensive scorched mussel beds with the associated
267 loss of shelters in Nuevo Gulf, it is likely that green crabs would exert strong predation
268 pressure on other native prey, and possibly upon the recruits of scorched mussels thus
269 preventing their re-colonization. Therefore, trophic-cascade type effects and
270 environmental stress (e.g. heatwaves) are likely interconnected as observed for other
271 regions (Cheng & Grosholz 2016). The rise in global heatwave events, combined with
272 the increasing number of invasions, could lead to important changes in community
273 composition and structure (Sorte et al. 2010; Sentis et al. 2021). Moreover, the
274 relationship between abiotic (e.g. physical stress) and biotic factors (e.g. predator-prey

275 interactions between native and invasive species) could trigger significant top-down
276 effects on rocky shores along the SWA.

277

278 **2.2. Effects of green crabs on the physical environment of soft bottoms**

279 Green crabs are considered allogenic engineers because they transform habitats
280 through their activities (Howard et al. 2019). Regardless of the mechanism involved in
281 these activities, green crabs can cause changes in the structure and composition of salt
282 marshes and mudflats, which may lead to erosion and degradation of important habitats
283 for many native species. This includes economically important and threatened fish and
284 bird species (Gotceitas et al. 1997; Heck et al. 2003; Kennedy et al. 2018). In addition,
285 numerous observations have linked high density of green crabs to a pronounced
286 widespread decline of salt marshes in both the Atlantic and Pacific coasts of North
287 America (Garbary et al. 2014; Neckles 2015; Matheson et al. 2016). The mechanisms
288 involved in this decline include habitat alteration, shredding blades, the dislodgements
289 of whole plants through bioturbation when foraging, and direct consumption (Davis et
290 al. 1998; Malyshev & Quijón 2011; Howard et al. 2019).

291 In Argentina, salt marshes are mainly dominated by the native *Spartina*
292 *densiflora*, the introduced *S. alterniflora*, and the cryptogenic *Sarcocornia* sp. (Bortolus
293 et al. 2009; Isacch et al. 2009; Bortolus et al. 2015, Fig. 1). Conducting regional
294 abundance estimations and targeted studies in salt marshes could accurately assess the
295 impact of green crabs on these ecosystems. This need is emphasised by documented
296 green crab herbivory in other regions, particularly their consumption of *Spartina* (Ropes
297 1968), and the increasing abundance of green crabs in salt marshes of Atlantic
298 Patagonia (Battini & Bortolus 2020). Additionally, these studies could evaluate whether
299 green crabs are capable of significantly reducing the area covered by these plants.

300 Future studies aimed at assessing the effects of green crabs by direct consumption
301 (analysing stomach contents of crabs inhabiting salt marshes) and/or altering the habitat
302 are necessary to evaluate the extent of potential impacts. In this regard, in northern
303 Patagonia, preliminary evidence suggests that green crabs appear to be more abundant
304 in salt marshes than on rocky shores (Müller Baigorria et al. 2022, M.E.M. unpubl.
305 data); hence the effects of green crabs on salt marshes represent a knowledge gap in the
306 invasion dynamics for the region. If the invasion continues northward, as is expected by
307 species distribution models, areas such as Anegada Bay (40°11' S), Bahía Blanca
308 estuary (38°45' to 39°25' S), Mar Chiquita coastal lagoon (37°32' to 37°45' S), and
309 Samborombón Bay (35°56' S) in Argentina, Santa Lucía salt marshes (34°51' S) in
310 Uruguay, and Lagoa dos Patos (31°09' S) in Brazil, are here identified as areas of high
311 importance in the early detection and future monitoring of this species (see marine
312 protected areas in Fig. 1). These wave-protected areas are particularly suitable for green
313 crab colonisation, in contrast to open shore wave swept coastlines (Young & Elliot
314 2020).

315 In the SWA, a native crab is also capable of modifying the physical environment
316 of soft bottoms. This is the case of the burrowing crab, *Neohelice granulata* (up to 40
317 mm of carapace width = CW), an endemic and dominant species of mudflats and salt
318 marsh ecosystems in the region (Bortolus & Iribarne 1999). Interestingly, the
319 geographic distribution of *N. granulata* spans from northern Patagonia in Argentina
320 (42°25' S; San José Gulf) through Uruguay to southern Brazil (22°57' S; Lagoa
321 Ararurama, Rio de Janeiro) (Spivak 2010). This distribution aligns with the current
322 green crab range and the possible northward expansion of green crabs in the SWA. At
323 present, both crabs are already coexisting in San Blas Bay, San Matías Gulf, and San
324 José Gulf.

325 *Neohelice granulata* is strictly associated with soft bottoms in estuaries, bays,
326 and coastal lagoons where halophyte grasses such as *Spartina* spp. form marshes in the
327 middle and/or upper intertidal zone (Boschi 1964; Spivak 2010). They occur in high
328 densities (>100 individuals/m², Bas et al. 2005) and dig burrows up to 1 m in depth
329 (Iribarne et al. 1997). This species is also a bioturbator, capable of removing large
330 amounts of marsh sediment while creating and maintaining burrows (Iribarne et al.
331 1997). Crab bioturbation by *N. granulata* and *Leptuca uruguayensis* (also a native crab
332 inhabiting soft bottoms, see section 2.3) plays a crucial role affecting the detritus
333 dynamics, particularly in mudflats. These environments are boundary systems between
334 salt marshes and open waters, where crabs are known as ‘deposit feeders’, mostly
335 consuming *Spartina* detritus (Botto & Iribarne 2000). In fact, *N. granulata* is mainly a
336 deposit feeder in mudflats, but a herbivore in salt marshes (Bortolus & Iribarne 1999).
337 Bioturbation has profound implications for the structure and functioning of these
338 systems because *N. granulata* modifies nutrient dynamics (Fanjul et al. 2011),
339 oxygenates sediments, which promote plant growth strategies, and thereby increases
340 plant productivity (Daleo & Iribarne 2009). Additionally, they play a key role in
341 plant/terrestrial-herbivore interactions (Daleo et al. 2007; Canepuccia et al. 2010) and
342 can modify nutrient loads of phreatic waters (Fanjul et al. 2008). They also translocate a
343 great amount of sediment for feeding purposes and gallery maintenance, influencing
344 substrate quality, penetrability, and transportation (Botto & Iribarne 2000).

345 With this context in mind, the likely arrival of green crabs to soft bottom
346 environments of the SWA will open a completely new scenario of biotic interactions
347 with native crabs. This is particularly significant given that burrowing and feeding pits
348 made by *C. maenas* can further alter benthic communities and reduce organism
349 abundance (Griffen & Byers 2009; Lutz-Collins et al. 2016). Forecasting potential

350 impacts in these systems is challenging; however, the displacement of native crabs, with
351 profound implications for ecosystem functioning, could be a likely outcome (see section
352 2.3).

353

354 **2.3. Interactions between green crabs and native crabs**

355 Interactions of green crabs with native and other invasive crabs are usually
356 species- and region-specific (Bélair & Miron 2009; Gehrel et al. 2016; Baillie &
357 Grabowski 2019). Green crabs are known to feed on a variety of organisms that are
358 important components of estuary food webs, including other crabs (Baeta et al. 2006).
359 This scenario can disrupt the delicate balance of these ecosystems and lead to cascading
360 effects on other species, as was mentioned above in section 2.1 for rocky environments.
361 On one hand, *C. maenas* is known to displace native crabs through predation and by
362 outcompeting them, not only for food but also for shelter. This phenomenon was
363 observed in North America with *Hemigrapsus oregonensis*, *Cancer magister*, and
364 *Dyspanopeus sayii* (Grosholz et al. 2000; McDonald et al. 2001; Jensen et al. 2002;
365 Gehrel et al. 2016), leading to local extinctions and significant declines in the
366 abundance of native crabs. On the other hand, in Canada, native crabs (*Cancer*
367 *irroratus*) and green crabs displayed distinct abundance patterns and appeared to avoid
368 each other, suggesting that both crab species can potentially coexist (Bélair & Miron
369 2009). There is even the paradigmatic case in the NW Atlantic coast where the recently
370 introduced Asian shore crab, *Hemigrapsus sanguineus*, has been implicated in the
371 displacement of the more established green crab (Baillie & Grabowski 2019).

372 Biotic resistance to invasions has also been documented where native crabs are
373 responsible for restricting green crab distributions in invaded regions (de Rivera et al.
374 2005; Jensen et al. 2007). For example, in California bays, the impacts of green crabs

375 appeared to be attenuated through predation and competition with native crab species
376 (*Cancer* spp.) (Jensen et al. 2007). Furthermore, in the NW Atlantic, green crabs have
377 encountered biotic resistance which prevents their southward spread since a native
378 predator (*Callinectes sapidus*) is limiting their abundance and distribution (de Rivera et
379 al. 2005). All these examples illustrate the wide array of scenarios in which green crabs
380 interact with other native and invasive crabs. The varied outcomes of these interactions
381 emphasise the importance of exercising caution when extrapolating results from one
382 region to another in predicting potential results.

383 In general, native crabs from the SWA are not conspicuous on the rocky
384 intertidal (particularly in the Magellanic biogeographic province, between 43–56 °S),
385 and decapods that inhabit these environments (less than 15 species) are usually smaller
386 than green crabs (Boschi 1992; Spivak et al. 2019). It is worth noting that green crabs
387 attain much larger sizes (more than double in some cases) than the majority of native
388 crabs with overlapping geographic and bathymetric distributions (but see the case of
389 *Ovalipes trimaculatus* in section 2.4). This size disparity will likely provide green crabs
390 with an advantage in predating and outcompeting native crabs both for food and shelter.
391 Taking into account its current distribution in Atlantic Patagonia, habitat preferences,
392 and feeding strategies, green crabs have the potential to adversely impact through direct
393 predation or competition for resources on several species of native brachyuran and
394 anomuran crabs (Barón et al. 2007). These include: *Pilumnoides hassleri*, *Peltarion*
395 *spinosulum*, *Leurocyclus tuberculatus*, *Cyrtograpsus altimanus*, *Cyrtograpsus*
396 *angulatus*, *Eurypodius latreillei*, *Leurocyclus tuberculatus*, *Lithodes santolla*,
397 *Halicarcinus planatus*, *Pachycheles chubutensis*, *Coenophthalmus tridentatus*, *Ovalipes*
398 *trimaculatus*, *Platyxanthus patagonicus* (Barón et al. 2007). Preliminary observations
399 suggest that two native and smaller crab species (*Cyrtograpsus altimanus* and

400 *Cyrtograpsus angulatus*, <50 mm CW), usually found on rocky shores, have seemingly
401 been reducing their population sizes across several areas, such as Puerto Madryn (42°S),
402 Camarones (44°S), Caleta Malaspina (45°S), and Puerto Deseado (47°S) (M.E.M. pers.
403 obs.). However, overall evidence quantifying the direct and/or indirect impact of green
404 crabs upon these native crabs is still lacking. This is particularly problematic since
405 species-specific baseline demographic data for native crabs is not available in already
406 invaded areas.

407 In soft bottom environments of the SWA, several native crab species are present,
408 including *N. granulata* (40 mm of CW_{max} see section 2.2), *L. uruguayensis* (15 mm of
409 CW_{max}), *C. altimanus* (25 mm of CW_{max}), and *C. angulatus* (42 mm of CW_{max}). These
410 species show a spatial segregation, where *L. uruguayensis* is usually present in the high
411 zone, *N. granulata* appears in the middle, and *C. angulatus* is usually found in the water
412 itself, but close to the shore (Boschi 1964). Important interactions occur among these
413 species, as *C. angulatus* is displaced from areas occupied by *N. granulata*, constituting a
414 clear example of competitive exclusion through aggressive interference (Iribarne et al.
415 2003). On the other hand, *N. granulata* affects *L. uruguayensis* by direct predation,
416 disturbance, and behavioural changes associated with predation risk, especially during
417 the reproductive season (Daleo et al. 2003). In light of the above, and with the likely
418 expansion of green crabs into soft bottom environments in the coming years, this
419 zonation pattern could be significantly altered. However, some sort of spatial and
420 temporal coexistence between green crabs and all these native species is expected to
421 occur at different sites in the foreseeable future.

422 In the SWA, no single native crab species appears capable of thriving along the
423 heterogeneous coastline as green crabs do. Green crabs demonstrate a unique
424 adaptability, occupying both rocky and soft substrates, as well as intertidal and subtidal

425 habitats simultaneously. Potential outcomes for native crabs as a result of the green crab
426 invasion can be challenging to predict; however, species-specific results based on their
427 life-history traits would not be surprising. If green crabs are capable of predating and
428 outcompeting native crabs in soft bottom environments, a similar scenario to that
429 observed in North America with *Hemigrapsus oregonensis*, *Cancer magister*, and
430 *Dyspanopeus sayii* (as mentioned above) could be possible. Green crabs already coexist
431 with *N. granulata* in San Blas Bay, Caleta de los Loros, San Antonio Bay, and San José
432 Gulf, which correspond to the southernmost geographic distribution of *N. granulata*,
433 although no evidence is yet available on their interactions. At least in Caleta de los
434 Loros and Playas Doradas, the number of *N. granulata* appears to have decreased since
435 the arrival of green crabs (Ariel Lappa, pers. comm. and N.B., pers. obs., respectively),
436 but evaluations are needed to confirm this. It also remains as an open question whether
437 the semi-terrestrial nature and burrowing ability of *N. granulata* might confer a
438 competitive advantage compared to green crabs.

439 The disparity in size between green crabs and most native crabs would not only
440 be an advantage for the former in terms of competition, but also in terms of predation
441 (Grosholz et al. 2000; Hunt & Behrens Yamada 2003; Ens et al. 2022). The diet
442 analysis of *N. granulata* indicates a primary consumption of sediment, *Spartina* sp., and
443 plant detritus, with limited crustacean detritus, while *C. angulatus* is primarily
444 annelidophagous but also preys on immature stages of *N. granulata* (Bortolus &
445 Iribiarne 1999; Schwindt et al. 2001; Barutot et al. 2011). Laboratory experiments also
446 revealed mutual predation between juveniles and adults of both species (Luppi et al.
447 2001). Given the smaller size of these native crabs and their limited crustacean
448 consumption, the possibility for one-sided predation by green crabs poses a threat to key
449 soft bottom crab species, especially if green crabs are preying on the recruits. For the

450 reasons mentioned above, green crabs have the potential to outcompete and prey on
451 native crabs along the SWA, which could lead to local extinctions and overall depletion
452 of native populations. However, interspecific interactions with other native predators
453 (beyond crabs) should be taken into account when assessing possible outcomes, as
454 discussed in section 2.8 referring to trophic subsidy.

455

456 **2.4. Effects of green crabs on sandy shore infaunal organisms**

457 Information on green crabs in sandy shores is limited compared to other
458 environments like rocky shores and salt marshes. Studies indicate that *C. maenas*
459 negatively impacts sandy shore organisms such as clams and oysters by preying on
460 small individuals, hindering recruitment (Hunt & Mullineaux 2002). *C. maenas* can eat
461 infaunal small clams and over 30 cockles per day (Walne & Dean 1972; Sanchez-
462 Salazar et al. 1987), and also influences the burrowing depth of cockles (Romano et al.
463 2011). It also alters nematode community structure through predation and sediment
464 modification (Schratzberger & Warwick 1999). Field studies have shown that early
465 benthic stages primarily feed on microfauna and juvenile macrofauna, while adults shift
466 to larger prey, with males favouring molluscs and females preferring annelids (Scherer
467 & Reise 1981). Experiments on the west coast of the United States revealed significant
468 reductions in bivalve, cumacean, and amphipod densities (Grosholz & Ruiz 1996;
469 Grosholz et al. 2000), while in Atlantic Canada, green crab manipulations indicate
470 severe, density-independent impacts on infauna, with native crabs potentially mitigating
471 these effects (Gregory & Quijón 2011).

472 In the NE Pacific, green crabs feed on clams (*Nutricula* spp.) that are a major
473 food source for shorebirds, so it is feared that if *C. maenas* becomes abundant, those
474 wading birds could be adversely affected (Behrens Yamada 2001). In the SWA, green

475 crabs may prey upon two native, small, and thin-shelled clam populations widely
476 distributed on sandy beaches: *Darina solenoides* and *Ardeamya pettitiana*. These species
477 represent the main prey items for several shorebirds that are highly dependent on
478 stopover sites for feeding during migration. For example, several shorebirds in coastal
479 sectors currently invaded by green crabs, such as the Red Knot (*Calidris canutus rufa*),
480 listed as Near Threatened at the global level (Birdlife International 2024) and as
481 Critically Endangered in Argentina (MAyDS and AA 2017), and the White-rumped
482 Sandpiper (*Calidris fuscicollis*), the Hudsonian Godwit (*Limosa haemastica*) and the
483 Two-banded Plover (*Charadrius falklandicus*), feed mainly on *D. solenoides*, and some
484 have *A. pettitiana* as secondary prey (D'Amico et al. 2004; Hernández & Bala 2007;
485 Hernández et al. 2008; Musmeci et al. 2013, 2015). Therefore, it is necessary to
486 evaluate the interactions between green crabs and small soft-shelled clams. In the SWA,
487 green crabs might affect infaunal populations by influencing their spatial distribution
488 and abundances with the ensuing effects on community structure, ecological
489 interactions, and even evolutionary processes, as has been predicted for other regions
490 (Grosholz & Ruiz 1995). In this regard, any change in densities of small invertebrates
491 arising from green crab predation may indirectly affect these migratory species, with
492 ecological implications extending far beyond the actual distribution range of green crabs
493 (Jamieson et al. 1998). As suggested by Grosholz et al. (2000), long term changes in
494 food abundance and the availability of alternative prey or foraging areas for shorebirds
495 should also be considered in future assessments of the potential indirect effects of green
496 crab invasion on shorebird populations.

497 In the SWA, green crabs share their habitat with other crab species in sandy
498 bottoms, such as *Ovalipes trimaculatus*, a native crab targeted by an important artisanal
499 fishery in north Patagonian gulfs included in the Valdés Peninsula Biosphere Reserve.

500 Given their similar body sizes, comparable behaviours, limb regeneration capabilities
501 (McVean 1976; Álvarez & Meruane 2009), and overlapping bathymetric distributions,
502 the potential for interactions exists, notably in terms of predation and competition.
503 Assessing the predator-prey dynamics between both crabs holds particular importance
504 for understanding the predatory impact of green crabs on fishery resources (see also
505 section 2.9). Additionally, it is crucial for evaluating whether *O. trimaculatus*, as a
506 predator, could potentially limit the abundance and distribution in areas of coexistence
507 between both crabs, thus potentially serving as a form of biotic resistance, as has been
508 observed in North America with other native crab species (de Rivera et al. 2005; Jensen
509 et al. 2007). In this regard, biotic resistance from native crustaceans (e.g. *O.*
510 *trimaculatus*) does not seem to be, at first glance, an important phenomenon given its
511 low abundance compared to green crabs in Nuevo Gulf (Malvé et al. in review).
512 Furthermore, in aquarium trials, adults of *O. trimaculatus* only prey on juvenile green
513 crabs after 12 days, in contrast to the voracious behaviour of green crabs towards them
514 (Malvé et al. in review). The apparent absence of native crabs capable of competing
515 with green crabs, not only for food but also for shelter, may have paved the way for a
516 rapid and successful invasion in the SWA. This scenario resembles that of South Africa,
517 where an open niche with potentially limited biotic resistance exists (Mabin 2018). In
518 the SWA, the absence of native species akin to green crabs may mitigate competitive
519 constraints, thereby possibly facilitating their spread.

520

521 **2.5. Implications of green crab invasion on the threatened Olrog's gull**

522 As mentioned above, green crabs can potentially affect the distribution and
523 abundance of native crabs (see section 2.3), which may translate into negative effects on
524 upper trophic level organisms that prey upon them. One of these species is the Olrog's

525 Gull, a mostly carcinophagous species endemic to the SWA. It feeds almost exclusively
526 on *N. granulata*, *C. angulatus* and/or *C. altimanus* during the breeding season (Delhey
527 et al. 2001; Herrera et al. 2005; Suárez et al. 2011), and complements its diet with a
528 variety of other prey types during the non-breeding season (Copello & Favero 2001;
529 Berón et al. 2012). The Olrog's Gull breeds only along the Argentinean coast in
530 colonies distributed in southern Buenos Aires Province and southern Chubut Province;
531 although over 98% of the population does so in the former sector (Yorio et al. 2013).
532 During the non-breeding season, it mainly disperses north along the coasts of Buenos
533 Aires Province, Uruguay and southern Brazil (Pacheco et al. 2009; Azpiroz &
534 Caballero-Sadi 2017; Copello et al. 2020). Because of its low population size (< 8000
535 breeding pairs), restricted distributional range, and population threats, the Olrog's Gull
536 is classified as Near Threatened at the global level (BirdLife International 2024) and as
537 Vulnerable in Argentina (MAyDS and AA 2017).

538 Green crabs are already widespread in the coastal areas where Olrog's Gulls
539 breed in San Jorge Gulf, Chubut Province (see section 1), and have recently invaded the
540 San Blas Bay Natural Reserve (see section 1), which marks the southern limit of the
541 main breeding grounds for Olrog's Gull in southern Buenos Aires. Lack of information
542 on current crab distribution patterns and on interactions between green crabs and native
543 crabs prevents the assessment of whether the invasion may affect the availability of key
544 prey for Olrog's Gull, potentially impacting populations of this threatened species.
545 However, Olrog's gulls have included green crabs in their diet (P.Y. & N.S. unpubl.
546 data), indicating the potential value of this species as a trophic subsidy (see section 2.8).
547 It is worth mentioning that throughout its distributional range, the Olrog's gull shares
548 breeding and feeding areas with the sympatric Kelp Gull (Yorio et al. 2013), an
549 abundant species with a generalist feeding strategy. Native crabs are not a relevant

550 component of the Kelp Gull diet (Yorio & Bertellotti 2002; Marinao et al. 2018; Yorio
551 et al. 2020), but recent studies have shown that green crabs can be an important prey
552 (see section 2.8). Further research is needed to explore the potential novel interaction
553 where Kelp Gulls may compete with Olrog's Gulls for key crab prey. Additionally,
554 considering the current pattern of northward expansion and predicted distribution (see
555 section 1), green crabs could also affect intertidal environments and the availability of
556 key prey for Olrog's Gull in its wintering areas, extending as far as southern Brazil.
557 This indicates the relevance of monitoring these environments for the early detection of
558 green crabs and the assessment of predator-prey interactions with the Olrog's Gull.

559

560 **2.6. Interactions between green crabs and other non-native species**

561 Once a non-native species establishes itself in a new area, it begins to interact
562 not only with native species but also with other non-native species already present in the
563 community. Examples of green crabs interacting with other invasive crabs in North
564 America have already been mentioned in section 2.3. In the SWA, interactions between
565 invasive species are beginning to emerge, creating a new and complex ecological
566 scenario. In the region, epibiosis and predation stand out as the two types of biotic
567 interactions involving green crabs and other already established invasive species that
568 merit further research.

569 Epibiosis has been detected on some carapaces of green crabs which were fouled
570 by introduced barnacles (M.E.M. pers. obs.). *Balanus glandula* has already been
571 described to foul the exoskeleton of the native crab *N. granulata*, (Mendez et al. 2014).
572 This barnacle has successfully colonised most of the Argentinean coastline, completely
573 re-shaping the native intertidal landscape (Orensanz et al. 2002; Schwindt 2007). It is
574 usually found on high levels of the rocky intertidal but has also successfully colonised

575 salt marshes (Schwindt et al. 2009). The settlement of epibionts is one of the major
576 issues influencing the life of *C. maenas*. The establishment of fouling organisms on the
577 crab's outer surface is a serious problem leading to several harmful effects (Greco et al.
578 2014). Negative effects of epibiosis include an enhanced susceptibility to predation and
579 a weakened competitive ability (Wahl 1997; 2008), among many others. Moulting is
580 crucial for growth, and is also known to be important in removing epibionts in aquatic
581 crustaceans (Bauer 2002). Therefore, negative effects of epibiosis would appear mostly
582 in crabs that have moulted for the last time in their lifetime because they lack the ability
583 to remove epibionts via ecdysis. It should be noted that epibiosis by barnacles
584 throughout its native range is conspicuous, with much more intensity in red morphs and
585 males ranging from a single to 159 epibiont barnacles per crab (Campos et al. 2022).
586 Considering the prevalence of epibiosis in its native region, a thorough study of
587 barnacle epibiosis occurrence in the SWA populations is necessary to ascertain whether
588 epibiosis constitutes a widespread phenomenon.

589 Green crabs are also preying upon other non-native species in the region, as was
590 preliminary observed on the sea slug *Pleurobranchaea maculata* (Battini & Bravo
591 2021), the acorn barnacle *B. glandula*, the polychaete worm *Eulalia viridis*, the isopod
592 *Sphaeroma* sp., and the amphipod *Ampithoe valida* (Cordone et al. 2022). Green crabs
593 have also been using *Undaria pinnatifida* as habitat/refugia in shallow subtidal areas
594 (Fig. 3); hence the extent of these interactions shaping ecosystem level responses is yet
595 to be understood. Finally, the interaction between green crabs and introduced oysters is
596 discussed below.

597

598 **2.7. Role of green crabs through infection and predation cycles on oysters**

599 Green crabs in both native and invaded areas can act as carriers of disease,
600 parasites, and bacterial infections which can be transmitted to native species and
601 potentially cause harm to local populations (Bojko et al. 2018). In its native habitat, *C.*
602 *maenas* is notable for its capacity to harbour a range of micro- and macro-parasites,
603 potentially acting as a disease vector and enabling parasites to persist in environments
604 shared with commercially important shellfish (Davies et al. 2019).

605 Considering the scenario of northward expansion, green crabs are expected to
606 reach Anegada Bay, the Bahía Blanca estuary, and Samborombón Bay (Fig. 1), where
607 beds of the native *Ostrea puelchana*, the invasive oysters *Magallana gigas* (Escapa et
608 al. 2004) and *Talonostrea talonata* (Cavaleiro et al. 2019) are established. Recently, the
609 presence of the ostreid herpesvirus-1 microvariant (OsHV-1 μ Var) was detected in wild
610 *M. gigas* in the Bahía Blanca estuary (38°45'–39°25' S) (Barbieri et al. 2019). This virus
611 is believed to be responsible for mass mortalities among early life stages of *M. gigas*
612 worldwide (Burge et al. 2007; Prado-Alvárez et al. 2016). Evidence of the role of *C.*
613 *maenas* hosting and potentially transmitting OsHV-1 is available at two Irish oyster
614 culture sites (Bookelaar et al. 2018), while the decline in oyster beds have been related
615 to *C. maenas* predation in Atlantic Canadian shorelines (Poirier et al. 2017). Hence, if
616 green crabs continue to invade northwards, it may open a completely new scenario of
617 potential synergistic negative effects, involving not only predation but also infection.
618 These potential predation-infection cycles in marine food webs may raise concern about
619 the status of economically important oyster beds and other shellfish fisheries in the
620 region (see section 2.9). Whether green crabs can locally reduce the spread of invasive
621 bivalves, such as *M. gigas* and *T. talonata*, through predation and/or infection of OsHV-
622 1, or at least diminish their population numbers remains to be determined. The same

623 scenario of predation and infection also applies for native oysters that could be
624 negatively affected.

625

626 **2.8. Green crabs as trophic subsidy for native predators**

627 Scant information is available about the consumption of green crabs by native
628 predators in coastal Argentina. Native predators may adapt to feed on introduced prey
629 when these become relatively abundant, thus non-native species can benefit native
630 species through trophic subsidy (sensu Rodríguez 2006; Carlsson et al. 2009). Several
631 native predators have been reported consuming green crabs both in native and invaded
632 regions, such as invertebrates, fish, birds, and mammals (Dunstone & Birks 1987; de
633 Rivera et al. 2005; Ellis et al. 2005; Klassen & Locke 2007; Young & Elliott 2020).
634 Limited information exists regarding the role of green crabs as a trophic subsidy for
635 native predators in the SWA, and future studies should address how this already
636 abundant and widely distributed species is modifying their trophic ecology. In addition,
637 research is needed on the potential role these native predators may play in biotic
638 resistance. Native predators include crabs, birds, fish, octopuses, and there is also
639 evidence of a sea lion handling a green crab (Fig. 3).

640 In the SWA, at least two gulls with different feeding strategies, the Kelp Gull,
641 *Larus dominicanus* (generalist), and the Olog's Gull, *Larus atlanticus* (specialist) are
642 regularly consuming this novel food resource (Yorio et al. 2020, see also section 2.5).
643 Studies conducted along a large coastal sector of the Chubut Province have shown that
644 *L. dominicanus* prey upon green crabs during their breeding cycle (Yorio et al. 2020;
645 Haro 2023, J.I.C. unpubl. data), and to a lesser extent during the non-breeding season
646 (Lisnizer et al. 2024). Green crabs are also consumed by the small population of the
647 carcinophagous *L. atlanticus* breeding in San Jorge Gulf (see section 2.5). Both gull

648 species largely forage in exposed rocky and mud intertidal substrates feeding mostly by
649 pecking (Copello & Favero 2001; Gatto et al. 2008; Suárez et al. 2014) and therefore,
650 predation pressure is mostly on green crabs distributed along exposed intertidal areas.
651 Furthermore, gulls have been observed preying on the uncovered intertidal, capturing
652 green crabs through plunge-diving or head submergence (J.I.C. pers. obs.).

653 Green crabs were also recorded in the diet of the White-headed Steamer-duck
654 (*Tachyeres leucocephalus*), listed as Vulnerable at the global level (Birdlife
655 International 2024) and as Endangered in Argentina (MAyDS and AA 2017), the
656 Imperial Cormorant (*Leucocarbo atriceps*), and the American Oystercatcher
657 (*Haematopus palliatus*) (Ibarra et al. 2018, J.I.C. pers. obs.), but its relative contribution
658 to the overall diet has not yet been quantified. Additional research is needed to explore
659 how avian predators, especially the abundant *L. dominicanus*, may influence the vertical
660 distribution of green crabs along the intertidal zone. Despite the benefits of green crabs
661 serving as novel prey for these gulls, the negative effects of green crabs on native gull
662 prey and the resulting changes in trophic interactions cannot be ruled out, especially if
663 the abundance and distribution of green crabs continue to increase.

664 Among teleosts, *Eleginops maclovinus* stands out as the most likely predator of
665 green crabs due to its diet and distribution in shallow waters. Preliminary results from
666 on-going sampling confirm their consumption (Fig. 3). *E. maclovinus* is a protandric
667 fish (Calvo et al. 1992; Gastaldi et al. 2009) that has an ontogenetic shift from carnivory
668 (juveniles and males) to omnivory, including abundant amounts of algae (Guzmán &
669 Campodonico 1974). This fish is associated with coastal canyons, where it approaches
670 to feed on bottom-dwelling organisms (Martin & Bastida 2008). Despite not appearing
671 to be a major predator of green crabs, and considering the substantial abundance of this
672 new prey in its feeding grounds, a dietary shift towards a more carnivorous diet is likely

673 to occur. This phenomenon has been observed in other instances, such as with
674 *Megaleporinus obtusidens* and *Pimelodus maculatus*, two omnivorous fishes that
675 increased their trophic positions following the invasion of *Limnoperna fortunei* in the
676 Uruguay River (González-Bergonzoni et al. 2023).

677 In Atlantic Patagonia, medium sized sharks and skates are primarily
678 invertivorous, with crabs being an important prey item (Sánchez & Prenskey 1996;
679 Belleggia et al. 2019; Pasti et al. 2021). The assemblage of coastal elasmobranchs
680 occurring in the shallow waters of central Atlantic Patagonia is composed of *Mustelus*
681 *schmitti*, *Myliobatis goodei*, *Sympterygia bonapartii*, *Sympterygia acuta*, and
682 *Callorinchus callorinchus* (Bovcon 2016). All of these species consume crabs such as:
683 *Coenophthalmus tridentatus*, *Cyrtograpsus altimanus*, *Ovalipes trimaculatus*, *Peltarion*
684 *spinosulum*, *Leurocyclus tuberculatus*, *Rochinia gracilipes*, and *Pachycheles*
685 *chubutensis*, with *M. schmitti* and *M. goodei* being the most carcinaphagous (Pasti et al.
686 2021; Pasti et al. 2023). Although recent gut content analysis of these species did not
687 reveal green crabs as a prey item (Pasti et al. 2023), it is worth noting that all the
688 samples were obtained from exposed beaches where green crabs are rare or absent.
689 Considering the current scenario of population increase and/or expansion of green crabs,
690 it would be necessary to carry out further sampling of coastal elasmobranchs caught at
691 less exposed sites or on beaches in the North Patagonian gulfs in order to correctly
692 assess the possible consumption of green crabs by these species.

693 In the case of invertebrate native predators, two native cephalopods (*Octopus*
694 *tehuelchus* and *Enteroctopus megalocyathus*) were reported consuming green crabs in
695 aquarium trials (N. Ortiz, pers. comm.). In digestive tract samples of *E. megalocyathus*
696 taken between 2004 and 2006 in intertidal areas north of San Jorge Gulf, a low
697 frequency of green crab remains was recognized (Ré et al. 2009). However, these

698 samplings were performed in the initial phases of the invasion, and the abundance of
699 green crabs has likely increased over the years. Therefore, a new evaluation of the
700 relative contribution of green crabs to the overall diet of octopuses is necessary. In the
701 fishing areas of Nuevo Gulf, green crab remains are frequently found in middens
702 outside octopus shelters, indicating octopus predation (Ortiz et al. 2024). Thus, although
703 green crabs can threaten native biodiversity and other local fishing resources, they could
704 also have a positive effect by increasing the food availability for *E. megalocyathus*
705 (Ortiz et al. 2024). Recent field sampling has also shown the coexistence of *O.*
706 *tehuelchus* and green crabs in shallow subtidal coastal areas of Nuevo Gulf. In addition,
707 aquarium experiments showed greater predation of *O. tehuelchus* on green crabs on
708 hard rather than soft substrate and on small sized crabs (Livore et al. in review).

709

710 **2.9. Interactions between green crabs and other human stressors**

711 Invasive species can interact and affect other anthropogenic stressors, such as
712 fisheries and tourism. The presence of green crabs has led to declines in fisheries and
713 aquaculture activities producing losses in the order of millions of dollars (Grosholz et
714 al. 2011). For example, *C. maenas* represents a threat to commercial bivalves of Canada
715 by predated on them (Miron et al. 2005) and was primarily responsible for the great
716 decline of the soft-shell clam, *Mya arenaria* in the US Atlantic coast (Floyd & Williams
717 2004; Wong 2013; Tan & Beal 2015; Young 2022). Green crabs also pose a potential
718 risk to the restoration of native Olympia oysters (*Ostrea lurida*) in the NE Pacific
719 because they particularly predate on small oysters preventing them to reach a
720 harvestable size (Snyder 2004). Similar potential impacts on bivalve fisheries were
721 reported in Australia (Walton et al. 2002; Campbell et al. 2019) and at mariculture sites
722 in South Africa (Griffiths et al. 1992).

723 In the northern gulfs of Atlantic Patagonia, numerous families rely on artisanal
724 fisheries, while in other instances, shellfish collection is pursued either as a
725 supplementary source of income or as a standalone hobby (Sánchez-Carnero et al.
726 2022). The negative effects of green crabs on artisanal fisheries in the SWA may
727 include several species, such as: the paddle crab *O. trimaculatus* (see also section 2.4),
728 native and invasive oysters (see also section 2.7), Tehuelche scallops (*Aequipecten*
729 *tehuelchus*), mussels (*Mytilus* spp.), reticulated clams (*Ameghinomya antiqua*),
730 octopuses (*Enteroctopus megalocyathus*, *Octopus tehuelchus*, see section 2.8), as well
731 as native whelks (*Buccinastrum deforme*). Most of these fisheries occur in the San José
732 Gulf, where the green crab invasion is relatively recent; however, a future increase in its
733 population beyond a certain threshold could negatively impact commercially important
734 target species and the people who depend on them. For example, green crabs are known
735 to have drastic effects on foundation species such as mussel beds, resulting in a decline
736 in their coverage (see section 2.1). This situation could reduce the abundance of
737 shellfish typically associated with these beds, thereby negatively impacting the
738 collection of these valuable resources by local communities. Whether green crabs can
739 benefit people who rely on fishing by providing a new resource remains unknown.
740 Experiences between native and invasive areas are contrasting. In Portugal, green crabs
741 (natives) are the most intensively fished species in the Ria de Aveiro lagoon, and the
742 catch per unit effort has decreased probably as a result of overfishing (Gomes 1991). In
743 North America, on the contrary, palate is not adapted to green crabs and there is at
744 present no established markets (Klassen & Locke 2007). However they have recently
745 been included on restaurant menus in recent years.

746 Tourism, another anthropogenic stressor, could also interact with the effects of
747 green crab invasion. This activity is especially developed in coastal cities, which have

748 become favourite tourist destinations mainly due to the attractiveness of their beaches.
749 Tourism serves as a primary economic driver for many cities, boosting local economies
750 and generating numerous direct and indirect job positions. In this regard, invasive
751 species can directly or indirectly contribute to habitat degradation and impacting
752 tourism resources (Katsanevakis et al. 2014). The shores along the Atlantic coast draw
753 thousands of tourists and recreationists who visit various destinations renowned for 'sun
754 and beach' tourism. The presence of green crabs at some of these sites, especially when
755 in high densities, can result in a loss of attractiveness of the beaches. Indeed, in various
756 tourist spots across northern and central Patagonia, such as Las Grutas and Puerto
757 Madryn, there have been recent reports of complaints from people, particularly children,
758 who have been pinched by crabs while entering the sea. Green crabs are also starting to
759 interfere with coastal recreational fishing, as they consume the bait before the target
760 species can reach it (M.E.M pers. obs.). Overall, the impacts of invasive species on
761 people's daily lives may help raise awareness and promote citizen participation in
762 activities aimed at ameliorating the impacts through prevention, monitoring, and rapid
763 response when needed (McKinley et al. 2017).

764

765 **3. Management decisions and the path forward**

766 Managing invasive species in the ocean is particularly challenging due to the
767 high connectivity of marine ecosystems across broad spatial scales, coupled with the
768 dispersal-facilitating nature of the water medium, which complicates efforts to control
769 biological invasions (Giakoumi et al. 2019). Working within an open system like the
770 marine environment imposes unique social, political, and technical constraints on
771 management decisions while the limited information available on the biology of marine
772 taxa and communities, leads to uncertainty regarding the outcomes of control (Thresher

773 & Kuris 2004). Coastal managers often express pessimism about invasive species
774 management because of the perceived openness of the system (Kuris 2003).

775 Prevention of new species introductions is considered the most cost-effective
776 strategy to manage biological invasions (IPBES 2023). Efforts to curb the impact of
777 invasive species on biodiversity and ecosystem services are ongoing, with the aim of
778 reducing overall introduction rates by 50% in 2030 through managing introduction
779 pathways and preventing the establishment of priority species
780 (<https://www.cbd.int/gbf/targets/6>). This is particularly relevant in marine ecosystems,
781 because once non-native species become established, subsequent management actions
782 are mostly unsuccessful. In just a few instances, early detection and rapid responses
783 yielded positive results, preventing the establishment of new species (Anderson 2005).
784 However, these occurrences are typically limited to small areas, such as enclosed bays,
785 inhabited by sessile or low-mobility organisms (e.g. Hewitt et al. 2005).

786 Post-establishment management actions are mostly ineffective (Sankaran et al.
787 2023). For example, an eradication program targeted at green crabs in California was
788 not only ineffective but resulted in stage-specific overcompensation and a 30-fold,
789 single-year increase in the population (Grosholz et al. 2021). In South Africa, despite
790 removing 36,244 green crabs, eradication was not achieved due to the large population
791 size, prohibitive nationwide eradication costs, and the latent possibility of reintroduction
792 (Mabin et al. 2020). In Canada, efforts to control green crab populations through
793 removal programs show short-term local benefits but struggle to achieve sustainable
794 suppression, often resulting in rapid population rebounds and shifts in size distribution,
795 highlighting the species' resilience as a persistent invader on larger scales (Tummon
796 Flynn et al. 2024). These experiences illustrate the difficulty, time-consuming nature,

797 and high costs involved in managing established populations of green crabs without any
798 guarantee that population numbers will drop in the long term.

799 In the SWA, the rapid expansion of green crabs is worrying, especially when
800 considering species distribution models that forecast their potential arrival to southern
801 Brazil and southern Argentina (Compton et al. 2010; Malvé et al. 2020; Vera-Escalona
802 et al. 2023). Therefore, the need to enhance prevention measures becomes paramount.
803 Emphasis should be focused on the pathway management in the movement of vessels,
804 together with long term monitoring and the implementation of rapid response protocols
805 in ports and adjacent areas. Recent studies have shown that marine non-native species
806 are present in all Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), and in some cases, this constitutes
807 the most significant anthropogenic stressor, regarded as an invasion hotspot within the
808 SWA (Reyna et al. 2023; Mendez & Schwindt 2024). For this reason, it is crucial to
809 establish priority areas where efforts need to be focused, considering that green crabs
810 are already present in several MPAs.

811 Target 3 of the Kunming-Montreal Biodiversity Framework states that MPAs
812 are expected to be effectively conserved and managed through well-connected protected
813 areas and other conservation measures, while target 6 aims to reduce the invasive
814 species introductions by 50% and minimise their impacts
815 (<https://www.cbd.int/gbf/targets>). The Argentinean coast comprises 68 MPAs
816 (<https://ampargentina.org/>) under various jurisdictions (municipal, provincial, and
817 national), most of which lack an active management plan, hindering the implementation
818 of a coordinated nationwide management strategy. The lack of awareness and
819 understanding of the impacts of invasive species, the dearth of information on best
820 management practices, and the absence of baseline information (Otero et al. 2013) pose
821 significant challenges in the management process. Although green crab impacts are not

822 yet fully understood, we have provided a comprehensive analysis of the potential
823 relationships and effects on environments and other species. In the light of its rapid
824 spread, preventive measures, as well as early detection and rapid response protocols, are
825 urgently needed, especially in high biodiversity valuable areas, such as MPAs.

826

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Draft

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1385 **Figure captions**

1386

1387 **Figure 1.** Map showing the spread of green crabs since its first detection at Comodoro
 1388 Rivadavia in 2000 assuming only one introduction event. Various substrate types—rocky,
 1389 gravel, sandy, salt marshes, and mixed beaches—are represented in different colours, as
 1390 provided by the Instituto Geográfico Nacional (<https://www.ign.gob.ar/>). Marine protected areas
 1391 are delineated in green: 1) Bahía Samborombón Natural Reserve, 2) Mar Chiquita Natural
 1392 Reserve, 3) Restinga del Faro Natural Reserve, 4) Centinela del Mar Natural Reserve, 5) Arroyo
 1393 Zabala Natural Reserve, 6) Bahía Blanca, Bahía Falsa and Bahía Verde Natural Reserve, 7)
 1394 Bahía San Blas Natural Reserve, 8), Punta Bermeja Reserve, 9) Caleta de Los Loros Reserve,
 1395 10) Bahía de San Antonio Natural Protected Area, 11) Islote Lobos National Park, 12) Puerto
 1396 Lobos Natural Protected Area, 13) Península Valdés Natural Protected Area, 14) Punta Loma
 1397 Provincial Reserve, 15) Punta León Natural Protected Area, 16) Punta Tombo Marine Protected
 1398 Area, 17) Patagonia Austral Interjurisdictional Marine and Coastal Park, 18) Rocas Coloradas
 1399 Natural Protected Area, 19) Punta Marqués Natural Protected Area, 20) Costa Norte de Santa
 1400 Cruz Natural Reserve, 21) Barco Hundido Provincial Reserve, 22) Monte Loayza Provincial
 1401 Park, 23) Cabo Blanco Natural Reserve, 24) Ría Deseado Natural Reserve, 25) Isla Pingüino
 1402 Interjurisdictional Marine Park.

1403

1404 **Figure 2.** Green crab observed and potential interactions with native and non-native species in
 1405 the SW Atlantic. Continuous lines represent relationships including green crabs, while dashed
 1406 lines indicate relationships in which green crabs are not directly involved. References: **a)**
 1407 **Processes:** P) Predation, C) Competition, TS) Trophic subsidy, E) Epibiosis, H) Herbivory, I)
 1408 Infection, EPE) Effects on the physical environment, AF) Artisanal fishery. **b) Species and**
 1409 **activities:** 1) *Larus dominicanus*, 2) shorebirds, 3) *Larus atlanticus*, 4) *Spartina* spp., 5)
 1410 *Neohelice granulata*, 6) *Buccinastrum deforme*, 7) *Ovalipes trimaculatus*, 8) *Darina solenoides*
 1411 and *Ardeamia petitiiana*, 9) *Enteroctopus megalocyathus*, 10) *Undaria pinnatifida*, 11) subtidal
 1412 mussel beds, 12) *Eleginops maclovinus*, 13) Rays, 14) Artisanal fishery by scuba diving, 15)

1413 *Magallana gigas*, 16) ostreid herpesvirus-1 microvariant (OsHV-1 μ Var), 17) *Cyrtograpsus*
1414 spp., 18) intertidal mussel beds, 19) non-native barnacles, 20) parasite *Agmasoma* sp.
1415

1416 **Figure 3.** Illustrative examples of interactions between green crabs and native and non-native
1417 species present in the SW Atlantic. a) Green crab consuming *Mytilus* spp. in a subtidal habitat,
1418 b) Green crab preying upon a native whelk (*Buccinastrum deforme*), c) Green crab consuming
1419 the non-native *Pleurobranchaea maculata* (published in Battini & Bravo 2021), d) Green crab
1420 preying upon a native whelk (*Tegula patagonica*), e) Green crab consuming a polychaete, f)
1421 Green crab using the non-native *Undaria pinnatifida* as substrate/refugia, g) Green crabs
1422 interact with native whelks for a polychaete (Echiura), h) Green crab fouled with non-native
1423 barnacles, i) Native whelks (*Buccinastrum deforme*) scavenging on a dead green crab, j)
1424 *Asterina fimbriata* scavenging on a dead green crab (photo provided by Ariana Alarcón), k)
1425 Native kelp gull preying upon a green crab, l) Green crabs recovered from stomach contents of
1426 *Eleginops maclovinus*, m) Native crab (*Neohelice granulata*) consuming a green crab, n) *Otaria*
1427 *flavescens* handling a green crab, o) Sea anemone (*Parabunodactis imperfecta*) feeding on a
1428 green crab, p) *Octopus tehuelchus* preying upon a green crab in an aquarium setting, q) Native
1429 crab (*Ovalipes trimaculatus*) eating a green crab.

Figure 1. Map showing the spread of green crabs since its first detection at Comodoro Rivadavia in 2000 assuming only one introduction event. Various substrate types—rocky, gravel, sandy, salt marshes, and mixed beaches—are represented in different colours, as provided by the Instituto Geográfico Nacional (<https://www.ign.gov.ar/>). Marine protected areas are delineated in green: 1) Bahía Samborombón Natural Reserve, 2) Mar Chiquita Natural Reserve, 3) Restinga del Faro Natural Reserve, 4) Centinela del Mar Natural Reserve, 5) Arroyo Zabala Natural Reserve, 6) Bahía Blanca, Bahía Falsa and Bahía Verde Natural Reserve, 7) Bahía San Blas Natural Reserve, 8), Punta Bermeja Reserve, 9) Caleta de Los Loros Reserve, 10) Bahía de San Antonio Natural Protected Area, 11) Islote Lobos National Park, 12) Puerto Lobos Natural Protected Area, 13) Península Valdés Natural Protected Area, 14) Punta Loma Provincial Reserve, 15) Punta León Natural Protected Area, 16) Punta Tombo Marine Protected Area, 17) Patagonia Austral Interjurisdictional Marine and Coastal Park, 18) Rocas Coloradas Natural Protected Area, 19) Punta Marqués Natural Protected Area, 20) Costa Norte de Santa Cruz Natural Reserve, 21) Barco Hundido Provincial Reserve, 22) Monte Loayza Provincial Park, 23) Cabo Blanco Natural Reserve, 24) Ría Deseado Natural Reserve, 25) Isla Pingüino Interjurisdictional Marine Park.

180x208mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 2. Green crab observed and potential interactions with native and non-native species in the SW Atlantic. Continuous lines represent relationships including green crabs, while dashed lines indicate relationships in which green crabs are not directly involved. References: a) Processes: P) Predation, C) Competition, TS) Trophic subsidy, E) Epibiosis, H) Herbivory, I) Infection, EPE) Effects on the physical environment, AF) Artisanal fishery. b) Species and activities: 1) *Larus dominicanus*, 2) shorebirds, 3) *Larus atlanticus*, 4) *Spartina* spp., 5) *Neohelice granulata*, 6) *Buccinastrum deforme*, 7) *Ovalipes trimaculatus*, 8) *Darina solenoides* and *Ardeamia petitiiana*, 9) *Enteroctopus megalocyathus*, 10) *Undaria pinnatifida*, 11) subtidal mussel beds, 12) *Eleginops maclovinus*, 13) Rays, 14) Artisanal fishery by scuba diving, 15) *Magallana gigas*, 16) ostreid herpesvirus-1 microvariant (OsHV-1 μ Var), 17) *Cyrtograpsus* spp., 18) intertidal mussel beds, 19) non-native barnacles, 20) parasite *Agmasoma* sp.

320x204mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 3. Illustrative examples of interactions between green crabs and native and non-native species present in the SW Atlantic. a) Green crab consuming *Mytilus* spp. in a subtidal habitat, b) Green crab preying upon a native whelk (*Buccinastrum deforme*), c) Green crab consuming the non-native *Pleurobranchaea maculata* (published in Battini & Bravo 2021), d) Green crab preying upon a native whelk (*Tegula patagonica*), e) Green crab consuming a polychaete, f) Green crab using the non-native *Undaria pinnatifida* as substrate/refugia, g) Green crabs interact with native whelks for a polychaete (*Echiura*), h) Green crab fouled with non-native barnacles, i) Native whelks (*Buccinastrum deforme*) scavenging on a dead green crab, j) *Asterina fimbriata* scavenging on a dead green crab (photo provided by Ariana Alarcón), k) Native kelp gull preying upon a green crab, l) Green crabs recovered from stomach contents of *Eleginops maclovinus*, m) Native crab (*Neohelice granulata*) consuming a green crab, n) *Otaria flavescens* handling a green crab, o) Sea anemone (*Parabunodactis imperfecta*) feeding on a green crab, p) *Octopus tehuelchus* preying upon a green crab in an aquarium setting, q) Native crab (*Ovalipes trimaculatus*) eating a green crab.

1128x931mm (72 x 72 DPI)